

Proposal

LISS panel grant 2023

Typifying rule-followers and rule-breakers: the effect of greed on rule-compliance

1 Layperson summary

For societies to adequately respond to pressing challenges like climate change, citizens need to follow behavioral rules, even when it involves personal sacrifices like reducing your carbon footprint. Rule violations are widespread, illustrating the need for a deeper understanding of when and why people follow rules. This project will examine the role of *greed*, the insatiable desire to acquire more. Greed is known to induce self-interested and unethical behavior, but does it also lead to rule violations, even when the benefits of violation are small? The first goal of this project is to **experimentally test the effect of greed on rule-compliance** in situations in which the gains of violation are high versus low. We test this using an incentivized experimental rule-following paradigm. Secondly, we aim to further **typify rule-followers and rule-breakers**, by correlating the measurements with a set of candidate personality traits and demographics previously measured in the LISS panel.

2 Background of the study and relationship to the literature

For societies to adequately respond to pressing challenges like the covid-19 pandemic and climate change, citizens need to follow rules that prescribe or proscribe behavior (“do this”, “don’t do that”). Rules help create social order¹⁻¹¹ and arguably are “the grammar of society”¹. Rules can be written or unwritten, are sometimes explicitly stated and sometimes implicitly assumed. Some rules, like the rules of law, can be actively enforced by authorities, while others are not. Most rules require individuals to incur costs, for example, by social distancing or reducing their carbon footprint. Despite the importance of rules for the maintenance of social order¹⁻¹¹ and achieving collective goals¹², it is unclear when and why people follow them.

Actual enforcement of rules by authorities (e.g., by monitoring behavior and sanctioning violations¹³⁻¹⁴) is often unlikely or even impossible¹⁵⁻¹⁷. Social order in societies, thus, largely depends on individuals following a rule voluntarily. Rule violations are widespread, yet, empirical evidence shows that voluntary rule-following is also common¹⁸⁻¹⁹. Even when people are asked to follow an arbitrary rule devoid of moral content, whilst they act alone and anonymously, and whilst following the rules is costly and violation hurts no-one, between 58 and 70 percent of people comply anyway¹⁸. This raises the following question: If people perceive an opportunity to benefit from violating a rule, why would they not take it?

It has been debated, controversially, throughout various disciplines, including philosophy, law, psychology, and economics, why people comply with rules that may contradict their self-interest^{1-2,5,7,20-24}. Previous work has suggested associations between voluntary compliance and individual’s sense of civic duty²⁵⁻²⁶, and their social preferences²⁷⁻²⁸. One largely overlooked possibility is that voluntary compliance is associated with an individual’s personality traits and demographics.

One plausible candidate personality trait might shape rule-following (and rule-breaking) is *dispositional greed*. Dispositional greed is defined as the desire to always acquire more²⁹. This desire can be directed towards obtaining more money or more material objects, but it can also be about non-material desires such as sex or status. Individual differences in greed can be measured using the Dispositional Greed Scale (DGS)³⁰. In 2013, a study with the LISS panel played an important role in the validation of the DGS. This scale was very well received, leading to a wide range of applications in studies of greed, including not only Dutch samples, but also samples from China, Japan, Russia and the USA³¹⁻³³. In 2019, the DGS was again included in the LISS panel in a study on the relationship between the motive of greed (and self-interest) in relation to antecedents and indicators of socioeconomic success³⁴⁻³⁵, which advanced the literature on what greed is and does. Overall, the DGS has proven to be a productive measure of individual differences in greed, across domains and across the globe, and predictive of a wide variety of relevant social, economic, and financial behaviors³⁰⁻³⁷.

People that are motivated by greed have been shown to be more easily lured into self-interested choices, unethical behavior, and even corruption.^{30,36-37} Hence, it seems plausible that greedy people are also more tempted than non-greedy people to violate a rule, even when the benefits of violations are only very small. Likely, non-greedy people need much higher gains of violation in order for them to consider breaking the rule. The first goal of this project is to test **the effect of dispositional greed on rule-compliance** in situations in which the gains of violation are high versus low. Studying this might help in tailoring deterrence policies and designing fitting interventions in order to increase rule-following. Greedy individuals might, for example, be more deterred by the threat of punishment (that offsets the tempting gain of violation), while for non-greedy individuals more benign interventions like education and awareness campaigns might also be effective.

A second goal of this project is to **explore who the rule-followers and rule-breakers are** by correlating the results of the “shooting star” paradigm with certain personality traits (e.g., BIG-V and optimism) and demographics (e.g., gender, income, and political preference) that were previously measured by the LISS panel. This information can help authorities design effective policies to promote rule-compliance

Over the last decade, several experimental tasks have been developed to study rule-following behavior, for example the traffic light paradigm¹⁸ and the bucket task³⁸. A limitation of these tasks is that the variable of interest is often dichotomous: someone either followed the rule (1) or not (0). The downside of such dichotomy is that an experiment requires many more participants to reach 80% power than a continuous outcome variable would require. We, therefore, developed an incentivized experimental paradigm to measure rule-following (called the “shooting star” task) with a continuous outcome variable. On top of the sample size advantages, this allows us to investigate not only rule-following and rule-breaking, but also rule-bending (i.e., breaking the rule a little bit without blatantly violating it: like driving 105 km/h when the speed limit is 100 km/h)). Pilot studies have successfully used the shooting star task to quantify rule-following tendencies among adults and children, and among Dutch, American and Czech participants. So far, most endeavors studying rule-following, including our own, made use of convenience samples (e.g., using students, online workers or museum visitors). Convenience sampling tends to introduce bias into your sample as it can be an overrepresentation of certain groups and an underrepresentation of others. As a result, this line of research might be less generalizable to the entire population. A third goal of this study is to **use continuous measure to study rule-following and to study rule-following in a representative sample.**

3 Research questions

The main research question examines the effect of dispositional greed on rule-following in situations in which the gains of violation are high versus low. Dispositional greed is the key predictor in our experiment, but our investigation also explores how rule-following may be shaped by other personality

traits and demographic variables. In particular, we will consider personality traits (e.g., BIG-V, optimism) and demographics (e.g., age, gender, income, political preference, and satisfaction with life) that were previously measured by the LISS panel. Thus, this project aims to typify rule-followers and rule-breakers (and rule-benders), looking at dispositional greed in particular and also exploring other personality traits and demographics that might relate to rule-following.

For our main research question, how does dispositional greed affect rule-compliance in situations where the gains of violating are high versus low, we have three hypotheses.

- Main effect of condition (high versus low benefits of rule-breaking): There will be more rule-breaking when the benefits of violation are high. People are more tempted when there is more at stake.
- Main effect of dispositional greed: People motivated by greed are more likely to break the rule than their less greedy counterparts. Greedy people are more tempted by the gains of violation than non-greedy people.
- Interaction effect: condition (high versus low benefits of rule-breaking) moderates the effect of dispositional greed on rule-breaking. That is, in the low stakes condition the effect of dispositional greed is stronger than in the high stakes condition. In the condition with low benefits of violation only the greedy individuals are tempted to violate the rule, whilst in the high benefits of violation everyone is tempted to break the rule.

4 Methodological approach

For this project we will make use of an incentivized experimental paradigm called the “shooting star” task to measure people’s rule-following behavior. The paradigm consists of two rounds: an “accuracy” round and a “rule” round. In the accuracy round (used to determine people’s initial bias), participants see an animated beam of light flashing by and are instructed to and rewarded for choosing the square that lights up most intensely. In the rule round, participants again see a beam of light flashing by. They are told that the rule is to choose the square that lights up most intensely. They can, however, earn more points by clicking on a square further to the right (with a maximum of 100 points in the low benefits of violation condition and 1000 in the high benefits condition if they click on the square that is most to the right). The differences between the “rule” round and the “accuracy” round is used as a measure for rule-compliance: a higher score indicates rule-breaking behavior.

We measure dispositional greed using the DGS²⁵. We will run a regression with a continuous variable for the extent to which people follow, bend, or break the rule as dependent variable, condition (high or low gains for violation; dummy variable), dispositional greed and the interaction between condition and greed as independent variables.

Furthermore, we will correlate the results of the experimental paradigm with existing LISS panel data on personality and demographics:

- BIG-V (IPIP, Goldberg), satisfaction with life (Diener), Values (Rokeach), Social Desirability (Marlowe-Crowne), and the LOT-R schaal (revised optimism scale from Scheier & Carver) from the Personality questionnaire (part of the LISS core study, most recent wave).
- Whether people see themselves as belonging to a church community or religious group and to what extent they would describe themselves as a religious or spiritual person, from the Religion and Ethnicity questionnaire (part of the LISS core study, most recent wave)
- If parliamentary elections were held today, for which party would they vote from the politics and values questionnaire (part of the LISS core study, most recent wave)
- Social Value Orientation (Murphy) from the 198 Motives for greed and self-interest questionnaire (assembled study, single wave)
- Background variables including, gender, age, personal income, household income, and highest level of education.

We aim for a sample that is representative of the general population as provided by the LISS panel in order to determine who the rule-followers and rule-breakers are and to draw conclusions that hold true for the broader population. A representative sample helps ensure that this project can accurately typify rule-followers and rule-breaking, increasing the reliability and relevance of this research. There are individual differences in how greedy people are, and these differences appear to be normally distributed in the population³⁹⁻⁴⁰. A representative sample will represent this distribution.

We aim for high statistical power. For our main research question regarding the effect of dispositional greed on rule-following, we performed a power analysis in G*Power for linear multiple regression with 3 predictors: with an effect size of .10 and an alpha level of .05 the default sample size of 2500 is adequate to reach 95% power. A power analysis in G*Power on the expected correlations (exploratory research question) revealed the same.

Preferably the fieldwork would be conducted before August 2024.

5 Implications for research, practice and/or society

Rules help create social order¹⁻¹¹ and especially during a crisis (like the covid-19 pandemic), it is important that citizens adhere to behavioral rules that either recommend specific actions (like wearing a facemask) or discourage certain behaviors (like not standing within 1.5 meters from each other). The prevalence of rule violations highlights the critical necessity for a more profound comprehension of the factors influencing why and when people follow rules. This project aims to uncover key predictors of

rule-following and rule-breaking, with a specific focus on dispositional greed. Answering this question has various implications for research, practice, and society.

First of all, this research leads to a deeper understanding of human behavior. It can help in identifying the underlying motives that influence individuals to conform or deviate from established rules. Secondly, results can inform the development of more effective policies and regulations. Understanding why some people adhere to rules while others do not, helps policymakers design interventions to encourage rule compliance and discourage rule-breaking. For law enforcement agencies, insights from this research can help better target their efforts and design incentive structures that align with the motivations of different individuals. Understanding the motivations of rule-breakers can also lead to more effective crime prevention strategies.

Non-greedy individuals may be more responsive to education and awareness campaigns, and policies promoting the ethical and moral aspects of rule-following, while greedy individuals may need stronger deterrents to offset the temptation of the gain of violating. For greedy individuals, policies might, thus, need to focus on creating strong and immediate disincentives for rule-breaking, for example punishment, fines, or other consequences.

Greed is an important economic motive that only recently (especially since the financial crisis of 2008) has been studied as individual differences at the psychological level. This project will help advance research in greed and will provide insight into what greed is and what it does, and more specially, how it is related to rule-following. Since dispositional greed has been measured by the LISS panel before (in 2013 and 2019), an additional contribution lies in the opportunity to determine the test-retest reliability. In order to evaluate the stability of dispositional greed over a period of 10 years.

6 Preliminary content of the LISS panel survey questions (optional)

We propose a 15-minute behavioral/survey study on the relationship between dispositional greed (and other personality traits and demographics) and rule-following. We make use of an experimental paradigm called the “shooting star” task. The paradigm consists of two rounds: an “accuracy” round and a “rule” round. In the accuracy round, participants see an animated beam of light flashing by and are instructed to and rewarded for choosing the square that lights up most intensely. Participants can earn 100 points when they indicate the most intense square, and with every square off they lose 10 points (with a minimum of 0 points). In the rule round, participants again see a beam of light flashing by (see Fig. 1 for a screenshot, will be translated in Dutch). They are told that the rule is to choose the square that lights up most intensely. They can, however, earn more points by clicking on a square further to the right (with a maximum of 100 points in the low benefits of violation condition and 1000 in the high benefits condition if they click on the square that is most to the right). Both rounds consist of 5 trials,

and in every round one trial is randomly selected in order to determine the points earned in the task. In order to incentivize choices, every point is worth a ticket in a gift voucher lottery (paid by the researchers). The experimental paradigm is estimated to last for 10 minutes.

Figure 1: the shooting star task. The rule is to choose the square that lights up most intensely, but participants earn more points by clicking on a square more to the right.

We discussed the technical possibilities with Boukje Cuelenaere: we will supply the code for the experimental paradigm (HTML and JavaScript) and this will then be implemented in LISS' surveytool Quest. Therefore, no extra agreements and data exchange is necessary.

Following the experimental paradigm, we include two individual questions (2 min). Responses are recorded on a likert scale from 1 = Strongly disagree (Helemaal mee oneens) to 5 = Strongly agree (Helemaal mee eens).

1. I was tempted to break the rule. / Ik kwam in de verleiding om de regel te overtreden.
2. People should follow the rules. / Mensen moeten de regels volgen.

Furthermore, we measure dispositional greed using the 7-item DGS²⁵ (3 minutes). Responses are recorded on a likert scale from 1 = Strongly disagree (Helemaal mee oneens) to 5 = Strongly agree (Helemaal mee eens). The rule-following paradigm and DGS are presented to participants in a counterbalanced order.

1. I always want more. / Ik wil altijd meer.
2. Actually, I'm kind of greedy. / Ik ben eigenlijk wel hebberig.
3. One can never have too much money. / Geld heb je nooit genoeg.
4. As soon as I have acquired something. I start to think about the next thing I want. / Zodra ik iets heb, denk ik alweer aan het volgende dat ik wil hebben.

5. It doesn't matter how much I have. I'm never completely satisfied. / Het maakt niet uit hoeveel ik heb, ik ben nooit echt tevreden.
6. My life motto is "more is better." / Mijn levensmotto is "meer is beter".
7. I can't imagine having too many things. / Ik denk dat ik nooit genoeg spullen kan hebben.

7 References

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